

**A STUDY ON MOBILE BANKING SERVICEQUALITY
DIMENSIONS OF NEW GENERATION PRIVATE
BANKS**

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INTRODUCTION

Today's world is one with increasing online access to services one part of this which is growing rapidly is '**Mobile Banking**'. Mobile banking is changing the banking industry and is having the major effects in Mobile banking with baking relationship In New Generation Private Banks. Mobile baking involves use of internet for delivery of products and services.

Mobile Banking is a cost-effective establishing channel for financial Institutions. Customers are enthusiastically the benefits of mobile banking. Mobile banking has empowers the banks to scale borders, change strategic behaviour and thus brings about new possibilities in new generation private banks. Banks are reorienting their business and also commercial offered by Mobile Banking.

The expeditious technological diffusion makes the internet is best way to provide customers with banking services delinquent of the limits of time and geography. Conspicuously the field of communication and information technology that ultimately led to the emergence of the idea of Mobile banking. Comparing to traditional approach, mobile banking is an economical straightforward way to conduct banking business, exchange of personalized information and buying and selling goods and services from any place at anytime.

MOBILE BANKING

A bank or financial institutions are providing mobile banking services. It allows manipulatingthe customer's financial transactions remotely using a Mobile device such as, Smartphone or tablet,

cellular phones. Its accessing by software commonly called an application (app) provided by the financial institution for the purpose. Mobile banking is usually available on 24/7 basis.

From the bank's concept, mobile banking reduces the cost of handling transaction by terminating the needs for customers to visit a bank branch for non-cash withdrawal and deposit transactions.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEMS

The banks have to pay more attention strengthening the quality of the services meeting the competition globally and locally. In developing environment of "consumer awareness leading to a greater degree of "Consumer Sovereignty", Customers are always dynamic and expect new services and self-contentment in the present services which leads the bankers to contemplate satisfy present and future needs of the customers by ensuring quality in service process delivery. The advent of liberalization, privatization and globalization the banks have to perform well so as to take competitive edge over other rival banks such as foreign banks and new private sector banks. Banking sector gets center of attraction over new schemes namely, direct money transfer scheme to the beneficiaries and financial inclusion.

Customer decides the destiny of the service provider. Customer get what is needed at the desired time, place and at the right price. 96% dissatisfied customers' do not complain and share with others. 91% dissatisfied customers never purchase goods and utilize the services again with the service provider. 82-95% customers' can be retained if they get a proper response. It costs 5 times to attract new customer than to retain the existing customer.

The Banks find very tough to deliver the M-Banking services to customers on the account of cut throat competition especially form the new generation private banks and foreign banks that excel in customer services. It is a great threat to private banks like ICICI being the largest bank in the new generation private banks which also face a threat from other private and foreign banks.

Hence, this present study focuses to study the Mobile Banking service quality of the banks over customers' perspective to assess their existing issues and their present grievances so that it can easily address the ongoing issues and meet the competition well. It focuses to identify the natural strengths and gifted services (Excellent Services) or very bad services offer to

customers and finding the reasons for being loyal and reasons for quitting from the study so that they can upgrade poor services and sustain the excellent services.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1 To know the mobile banking service quality facilities given by private banks
- 2 To know the private banks transforming digital services activity in new generation
- 3 To know the wants and needs of service quality in new generation private banking customers
- 4 To measure the service quality of mobile banking activities in new generation.
- 5 To know the improvements in service quality suggested by banking customers to private banks

SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study was confined to Vellore city. Latest information and data collection was taken for this study. Coverage was given in the study to include the target allocation sector-wise viz. New generation private banking service sector. The study also focuses attention on the performance of the private banks in the banking services. The analysis is based on the new generation private banks. Limitations of the study were that the beneficiaries were interviewed so as to obtain their opinion about the function of this study on Vellore city.

In this study belong mobile banking activities in new generation private banks on Vellore city only. And the study refers information, collecting data, and other activities done around on Vellore city only.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted based on the secondary data. For the purpose of collecting information required for the study, the private banks in Vellore city has been referred to. In addition to these sources, the researcher referred to many articles, research studies and reports,

COMMONWEALTH JOURNAL OF COMMERCE & MANAGEMENT RESEARCH

Vol.5, Issue 10 (October 2018)

ISSN: 2393-851X

Impact Factor: 4.382

which have proved to be immense help to gain background knowledge of the topic. The data collected was analyzed by SPSS.

Research Design

The research design is empirical in nature since the study is conducted using both analytical and diagnostic research types. The study is conducted in a two stage format, with a preliminary pilot study followed by the main study. The major part of the study is based on the primary data.

Study Area

The Vellore city has been chosen for the purpose of study because of the following reasons:

- The city has become the financial and business hub of the entire State.
- The financial literacy of the people of Vellore city is conducive for the purpose of study.
- The banking habits of the residents of the Vellore city are quite similar to that of the people placed in the rest of India.

Hence, it is considered highly appropriate to conduct the study in the Vellore city.

Sources of Data

Primary data have been collected from the Customers of the private banks in the Vellore city. Secondary data was collected from various published and unpublished sources which include Journals, Magazines, Publications, Reports, Books, Dailies, Periodicals, Articles, Research Papers, Web sites, Bank Publications, Manuals and Booklets.

Sampling Technique and size

Simple Random Sampling Method was adopted to collect the primary data. The respondents for the purpose of the study are selected randomly. Totally 100 questionnaire were issued and collected the responses from the private banks customers in Vellore city.

Questionnaire

Well-structured questionnaire have been used for the purpose of the study. The data were collected from the Mobile banking customers.

Questionnaire Design

To collect the primary data, a questionnaire was designed with **four** Sections. **Section I** contains demographic characteristics with optional questions. The **second Section** consists of the M-Banking Service Qualities of the customers in Vellore City with variables in the four points Likert's scales such as Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and No opinion type questions. The **third Section** consists of factors influence in what do you feel about m-banking services with nine variables in the five points Likert's scales such as 'Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and No opinion'. The fourth section consists of factors influence in problems in m-banking services with ranking scales.

Analysis of Data

The primary data collected from the respondents are analyzed by applying the statistical tools.

Simple percentage analysis is applied to find out the demographic profile M-Banking customers in Vellore district.

1. **Cross tab percentage analysis** is implemented to find out the association between the demographic profile and its awareness level over the clusters of service quality of M-banking customers.
2. **T-test** is applied to analyze the level of influence of factors for switching the brand, the impact of new car brand preference and level of satisfaction for the new car.
3. **ANOVA** is used as an instrument for analyzing the influence of demographic variables on service quality dimension.
4. **Multiple Regression Analysis** is applied to find out the influence of service quality on usage of M-banking services.

MOBILE BANKING SERVICES AND ITS TREND

Mobile banking, which is an integral part of m-Commerce, has become very popular among mobile users ever since its existence in 2007. It creates a new, convenient communication and fast financial transactional channel for mobile users, which is accessible anywhere, anytime,

Checking account information, balance available, credit/debit card information, cheque status, setting alerts, payment reminders, ascertain ATMs and bank branches, accessing mini statement, accessing loan and equity statements, insurance policy management, or placing orders for cheque books, via mobile phones are some of the services offered in mobile banking. With multiple access channels, such as SMS and mobile internet (WAP) mobile, banking is encouraging mobile users more to explore the service. [1]

SERVICES PROVIDED BY NEW GENERATION PRIVATE BANKS

- Provides information with care and attention
- Immediate help for problem or queries
- Connects immediately to bank accounts
- Prompt responses for online requests
- Restricts unauthorized access
- Accurate record
- Updated information
- Relevant and accurate information
- Safe with online transaction
- Secure in providing personal information
- Service systems are easy to use
- Easy navigation through web pages
- Systems are clear and understandable
- Facilitates online shopping, payments, investments, and other activities

DIMENSIONS OF SERVICE QUALITY

The SERVQUAL scale was developed by Parasuraman in 1985, and refined in 1988, 1991 and 1994 which would be used to exploit service quality over a spacious range of service categories. Within the SERVQUAL model, service quality is defined as the gap between customer perceptions of what occur during the service transaction and his prospect of how the

COMMONWEALTH JOURNAL OF COMMERCE & MANAGEMENT RESEARCH

Vol.5, Issue 10 (October 2018)

ISSN: 2393-851X

Impact Factor: 4.382

service transaction should have been performed. Preliminarily 10 proportions of service quality were proposed (reliability, responsiveness, competence, access, courtesy, communication, credibility, security, understanding the consumer, and tangibles). Later these were reduced to five (reliability, responsiveness, empathy, assurances and tangibles). The later model of five quality dimensions (RATER) considered the following issues: **R: Reliability:** Endowment to accomplish the promised service dependably and accurately. **A: Assurance:** Ability, knowledge and politeness of employees to inspire trust and confidence. **T: Tangibles:** Physical concern, equipment and department of employees. **E: Empathy:** Peculiar, caring attention that the firm Proffers to its customers. **R: Responsiveness:** Capability to help consumers and anticipate timely service.

I. DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
1. GENDER			
Male	64	64.0	64.0
Female	36	36.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	
2. AGE			
18-25	39	39.0	39.0
25-35	53	53.0	92.0
Above 35	8	8.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	
3. OCCUPATION			
Government servant	21	21.0	21.0
Professional	23	23.0	44.0
Self-employed	15	15.0	59.0
Others	41	41.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

4. EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION			
Below HSC	5	5.0	5.0
Graduate	86	86.0	91.0
Above Graduate	9	9.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	
5. INCOME			
Below 20000	58	58.0	58.0
Above 20000	39	39.0	97.0
Above 45000	3	3.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

Inference

It is found from that 64% of the respondents are male and 36% of the respondents are female. Thus, the majority of the respondents are male in the study area.

It is found that 39% of the respondents are in the age group of 18-25 years and 53% of the respondents are in the age group of 25-35 years and 8% of the respondents are in the age group of above 35 years. Thus, the majority of the respondents are in the age group of 25-35 years in the study area.

It is found that 21% of the respondents are Government servants and 23% of the respondents are professionals and 15% of the respondents are self-employed and 41% of the respondents are others. Thus, the majority of the respondents are others in the study area.

It is found that 5% of the respondents have below HSC as educational qualification and 86% of the respondents are Graduate and 9% of the respondents are above Graduate. Thus, the majority of the respondents are Graduate in the study area.

It is found that 58% of the respondents have below 20000 as monthly income and 39% of the respondents have Above 20000 and 3% of the respondents have Above 45000. Thus, the majority of the respondents have below 20000 as monthly income in the study area.

II. SERVICE QUALITY

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
1. Relevant and accurate information			
Strongly agree	82	82.0	82.0
Agree	18	18.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	
2. Updated information			
Strongly agree	79	79.0	79.0
Agree	21	21.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	
3. Accurate record			
Strongly agree	64	64.0	64.0
Agree	36	36.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	
4. Restricts unauthorized access			
Strongly agree	72	72.0	72.0
Agree	25	25.0	97.0
No opinion	1	1.0	98.0
Disagree	2	2.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	
5. Prompt responses for online requests			
Strongly agree	83	83.0	83.0
Agree	17	17.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	
6. Connects immediately to bank accounts			
Strongly agree	75	75.0	75.0

COMMONWEALTH JOURNAL OF COMMERCE & MANAGEMENT RESEARCH

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Agree	25	25.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	
7. Immediate help for problem or queries			
Strongly agree	16	16.0	16.0
Agree	74	74.0	90.0
Disagree	10	10.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	
8. Provides information with care and attention			
Strongly Agree	81	81.0	81.0
Agree	18	18.0	99.0
No opinion	1	1.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	
9. Safe with online transaction			
Strongly agree	57	57.0	57.0
Agree	43	43.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	
10. Secure in providing personal information			
Strongly agree	52	52.0	52.0
Agree	46	46.0	98.0
Disagree	2	2.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	
11. Service systems are easy to use			
Strongly agree	67	67.0	67.0
Agree	32	32.0	99.0
Disagree	1	1.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

12. Easy navigation through web pages			
Strongly agree	29	29.0	29.0
Agree	59	59.0	88.0
Disagree	12	12.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	
13. Systems are clear and understandable			
Strongly agree	67	67.0	67.0
Agree	33	33.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	
14. Facilitates online shopping, payments, investments, and other activities			
Strongly agree	56	56.0	56.0
Agree	43	43.0	99.0
Disagree	1	1.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

Inference

It is found that 82% of the respondents are strongly agreed about relevant and accurate information and 18% of the respondents are agreed.

It is found that 79% of the respondents are strongly agreed about updated information through mobile banking and 18% of the respondents are agreed.

It is found that 64% of the respondents are strongly agreed about accurate record in mobile banking services and 36% of the respondents are agreed.

It is found that 72% of the respondents are strongly agreed about restriction of unauthorized access, 25% of the respondents are agreed, 1% of the respondents have no opinion and 2% of the respondents are disagreed.

It is found that 83% of the respondents are strongly agreed about prompt responses for online requests and 17% of the respondents are agreed.

It is found that 75% of the respondents are strongly agreed about mobile banking services connected immediately and 25% of the respondents are agreed.

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It is found that 16% of the respondents are strongly agreed about immediate help for problem or queries by new generation private banks and 74% of the respondents are agreed and 10% of the respondents are disagreed.

It is found that 81% of the respondents are strongly agreed about the new generation private banks provide information with care and attention, 18% of the respondents are agreed, 1% of the respondents have no opinion.

It is found that 57% of the respondents are strongly agreed about safe with online transaction by the new generation private bank and 43% of the respondents are agreed.

It is found that 52% of the respondents are strongly agreed about secure in providing personal information by the new generation private bank and 46% of the respondents are agreed and 2% of the respondents are disagreed.

It is found that 67% of the respondents are strongly agreed about service systems of new generation private bank are easy to use, 32% of the respondents are agreed and 1% of the respondents are disagreed.

It is found that 29% of the respondents are strongly agreed about easy navigation through web pages of new generation private bank and 59% of the respondents is agrees and 12% of the respondents are disagreed.

It is found that 67% of the respondents are strongly agreed about systems are clear and understandable in new generation private banks and 33% of the respondents are agreed.

It is found that 56% of the respondents are strongly agreed about new generation private banks facilitates online shopping, payment, investments and other activities, 43% of the respondents are agreed and 1% of the respondents are disagree.

CONCLUSION

It is well acknowledged that mobile phones have immense potential of conducting financial transactions thus leading the financial growth with lot of convenience and much reduced cost. For inclusive growth, the benefits of mobile banking should reach to the common man at the remotest locations in the country. For this all stakeholders like Regulators, Government telecom service providers and mobile device manufactures need to make efforts so that penetration of mobile banking reaches from high-end to low-end users and from metros to the middle towns and rural areas. There is also need to generate awareness about the mobile

banking so that more and more people use it for their benefit. Since last five years mobile telephone service extended tremendously in India and it provides golden opportunities to extend m-banking service in India.

The M-banking services are very popular among the new generation Private Bank customers. It offers convenient services, quick service and improves the customer satisfaction. Since the researcher revealed that customers always seek their convenience in the form of quick and perfect services. It is suggested that each branch of public, private and foreign banks should organize a periodic awareness program with the introduction of innovative services. After reaching the point of culmination of research within the limited period the present research open fascinating vistas as for future research in the future. If this is done in future there is a possibility the usage of Mobile Banking Will go up to 100%.

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COMMONWEALTH JOURNAL OF COMMERCE & MANAGEMENT RESEARCH

Vol.5, Issue 10 (October 2018)

ISSN: 2393-851X

Impact Factor: 4.382

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20. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, Volume 3, Issue 1, January 2013 1 ISSN 2250-3153 www.ijsrp.org Mobile Banking Services as Adoption and Challenges: A Case of M-Banking in India (Positive and Negative impacts, Mobile Growth in India, Adoption Models and Mobile Technology) Dr. Vinod Kumar Gupta* , RenuBagoria** , NehaBagoria***